

Insights from International Transfer Pricing through Systematic Review and Bibliometric Analysis

RAFI FAROOQ, KHALID ASHRAF CHISTI AND FIRDOUS AHMAD HURRAH

Abstract : *This study attempts to gather and analyze the available literature on the topic in order to convey the current status of Transfer Pricing issues through systematic literature review and bibliographic analysis. This evaluation sheds light on the prominent authors, region, organizations, sources, and publications by using bibliometric data from 128 research publications across the world. Web of science database was utilized for the literature collection over the period of 33 years. It was revealed that centrality of transfer pricing revolves around the tax avoidance and our analysis shows that TP should be utilized strategically in planning, manufacturing, and income generating, rather than as a technique of tax evasion.*

Keywords : Systematic Review, Bibliometric Analysis, Transfer Pricing, Multinational Corporation, Tax Compliance, Tax Management Strategy.

1. Introduction

At the very outset, transfer pricing can be defined as transfer pricing is the process of setting the price at which an enterprise transfers physical goods and intangible property or provides services to an associated enterprise (OECD, 1979). Multinational corporations setting their transfer prices have been a hot topic for decades because it ignores the market forces while setting the prices for intra-firm transactions (Benari 2009). According to Richardson, Taylor, and Lanis (2013), multinational corporations may engage in intra-firm trade by including price payments in order to aid tax evasion via fictitious inter-company transfer pricing. Transfer pricing has evolved as a strategy to shift the resources

Rafi Farooq, Research Scholar at Department of Commerce, University of Kashmir, Srinagar, India - 190006. E-mail : Rafifarooq786@gmail.com

Dr.Khalid Ashraf Chisti, Assistant Professor, Department of Commerce, University of Kashmir, Srinagar, India - 190006. E-mail : Chistikhalid@kashmiruniversity.ac.in

Firdous Ahmad Hurrah, Research Scholar at Department of Commerce, University of Kashmir, Srinagar, India - 190006. E-mail : Afirdous75@gmail.com

of an MNC to its entities setup in various foreign countries (Copithorne, L.W. 1971). Worldwide, a large number of the MNCs have registered their branches in tax havens to obtain tax benefits. The existence of tax havens is perhaps one of the incentives that decide for a company to become multinational. The abuse of transfer pricing has become a global issue as it results in the erosion of the country's tax base and profit shifting (Sebele, 2021). Manipulation of prices between the related parties on the non-market basis as against the arm lengths price resulted in reduced organization's tax liability by shifting a significant portion of their earnings into low tax countries. This tax minimization strategy has played a vital role in the over-reporting and under-reporting of payments in a particular economy resulting in the misallocation of resources across time and space. MNCs practicing the transfer pricing, have addressed to several non-tax objectives also, such as economic objectives to attain the efficiency in the allocation of costs and resources, avoiding exchange rate volatility Devi and Suryarani (2020), and organizational objectives in achieving the internal management and international orientation, management control, risk management, fund management. (Pendse,2012; Cravens, 1997; Lin and chang, 2010).

Accordingly, this review has been taken up to capture the existing literature on transfer pricing systematically because the previous review on the title has several limitations; for example, Grabski's (1985) review on transfer pricing was limited to 9 years only (1975-1983). Dr Subha Kant Padhi's (2019) study did not employ the systematic review technique as the author tries to clarify the numerous theoretical models created to handle the challenges of transfer pricing. Furthermore, Delina Herdian Septiani's (2021) review on transfer pricing included only 36 articles and was limited to only five years (2016-2021). Therefore, this paper develops a network of transfer pricing literature through systematic review wherein the current status of transfer pricing can be traced along with future research agenda. More importantly, this review also includes the bibliometric analysis to identify the essential authors, countries, and journals, which may prove essential and helpful to scholars, managers, and policymakers in tracking the stock of transfer pricing and developing an informed understanding of the topic and its progress over time. This paper attempts to answer the following research questions.

1. What does existing research inform us about transfer pricing?
2. How many publications are there for the title of this research during last 4 decades?

3. Who are the most influential authors?
4. Where are the most articles published country-wise and journal wise?
5. What is the rise in publications over time?
6. What is the future agenda to be explored on transfer pricing?

The rest of this review is organized as follows. First, we provide a review of the transfer pricing literature. The bibliometric approach employed in this review is then described. After that, we will show the findings of a bibliometric analysis and finally, we present a research plan for the future to broaden the scope of TP.

2. Literature Review

In the globalized world, MNCs have begun to operate worldwide, and Transfer pricing emerged as a mechanism for multinational corporations (MNCs) to relocate their revenue from high-tax countries to low-tax jurisdictions to reduce their tax obligation (Bhat 2009). According to Copithorne, L.W. (1971), the application of corporate taxes and various management efforts might drive transfer prices. The talks proceeded, and (S.lall 1973) attempted to identify the numerous possible causes, such as effective tax rates, tariff rates, and currency rates, that require an MNC to move profits through transfer pricing. (Grubert & Mutti, 1991) analyzed the ability to shift profits from high-tax countries to low-tax countries and indicated that taxes and tariffs play an essential role in determining multinational operations. (Harris 1993) hypothesizes that a decrease in the U.S tax rate from 46% to 34% incentivizes the MNCs to shift income into the U.S through transfer pricing. Likewise (Jacob, 1996) found that transfer pricing as the mechanism for income shifting. Clausing (2001) establishes a clear relationship between the tax rates and intra-firm trade; results indicate that the U.S has an unfavorable intra-firm trade balance with low-tax countries. Similarly (Overesch, 2006) Identified transfer pricing as a special profit-shifting channel. Pradeep Gupta (2012) observed that the differential in corporate tax rates across countries and variations in custom duty across various products encourage the MNCs to manipulate the transfer pricing between the affiliated firms to minimize the taxable income of the whole group. (Egger & Seidel, 2013) found the increased share and volume of bilateral intra-firm trade (5.5%) when corporate tax rates differ between home and host country. (Vicard 2014) provided direct evidence of profit shifting to low tax countries through transfer pricing. There are some

studies in which different objectives have been associated with transfer pricing other than tax motivations. For example, Donnenfed et al. (1995), shows that internal factors like coordination and monitoring between headquarters and subsidiaries have their bearing on transfer pricing. (Cravens, 1997) found that MNEs consider several factors, such as internal management and international orientation and tax management, when deciding on transfer pricing. Likewise, Lin and Chang (2010) explored internal and external motivations for transfer pricing manipulations; the study results indicated that tax minimization is no longer the focus objective of transfer pricing manipulation. (Pendse, 2012) finds a strong impact of various non-tax purposes (management control, risk management, fund management) on transfer pricing decisions of MNCs. Several firm-level characteristics also impact transfer pricing (Grant Richardson et al., 2013), showing that firm size, profitability, leverage, intangible assets, and multi-nationality are significantly positively associated with transfer pricing aggressiveness.

The extensive literature documented both internal and external factors that MNCs genuinely consider while setting their transfer price for intra-firm transactions in goods, services, and intangibles. The existence of tax differentials between nations allows MNCs to reduce their worldwide tax burden by shifting money from high tax states to low tax nations via manipulation of transfer pricing. This manipulation of transfer prices is done to bypass regulatory limitations and take advantage of variations in tax rates between countries. It is highly recognized that tax liability minimization is the primary goal of transfer pricing practices; however, using the non-arm's length pricing in international transfer pricing is not restricted to taxability management. There are diverse and varied determinants for transfer pricing, including coordination between subsidiary and parents, strategic management, control management, intangibles, leverage, size of firms, Multinationality, and risk management.

A bibliometric review of TP research is conducted to explain the TP literature further. It has emerged to be the modern approach for examining and interpreting vast amounts of data. It allows us to explore the evolution of a particular discipline while also offering light on developing topics in that field. However, its use in business research is still very young and, in many cases, inadequate. As a result, we want to provide an overview of the bibliometric methodology and step-by-step process. The review's precise methodology and procedures are discussed in the following sections.

3. Methodology

In early 2022, a simple search on the subject using the keyword “Transfer Pricing” yielded 413 publications included in the literature review process. The search technique had many types of research with varying periods, conceptual and methodological features, and four phases of filtration were employed to get the final findings, namely Filtration of databases, Scholarly filtration, Filtration by subject, and Language filtration.

3.1. Database Search

Web of science being the world’s oldest database was selected for the study. The database is most widely used and authoritative database of research publications and citations (Caroline Birkle 2020) and its richness of bibliometric information for publication.

3.2. Scholarly Filtration

To reduce the irrelevant material and achieve knowledge diversity on the topic, only journal papers and conference proceedings were used, since they are often appraised based on innovation and are submitted to rigorous peer review, which assists us in extracting quality insights. In case of book chapters, notes, newsletters etc., the scholarly filtration excluded 17 articles and retained 191 articles for further analysis.

3.3. Subject Filtration

Subject filtration includes the broader area of Economics, Business finance, Management, Operations research, management science, and Business. These subjects categorized by web of science contain the transfer pricing at its broadest and are relevant to the business. This filtration has been done in accordance with (Paul. et al.2021). In subject filtration, 132 articles were retained that belonged to the subjects mentioned above, and 59 articles were removed.

3.4. Language Filtration

Language filtration was done to remove the articles written in a non-English language. Language filtration has been done in line with (Mukherji, et al. 2021)

Figure-1 : Search and Filtration Strategy for Bibliometric Analysis

As a result, 80 items were removed due to academic, language, and subject filters. The remaining 128 papers that passed the screening procedure are now being prepared for bibliometric evaluation. In this review, the TP literature was examined bibliometrically, (See Fig. 2). We performed several bibliometric-based analyses on 128 publications that made it through the screening procedure during the web of science bibliometric search. We concentrated on publishing TP research articles, worldwide citation, and social network analysis, as well as significant contributors (authors, nationalities, and institutions). Furthermore, we used the VOS viewer to gain a better understanding of the critical contributors and publications by analyzing co-authorship based on authors and countries, along with citation analysis.

Figure-2 : Analysis Structure for Bibliometric Analysis

3.1. Publication Trend

Publication trend based on the year wise publication of articles reveals an asymmetric pattern of increase or decrease in transfer pricing publications over time see, figure-3. The highest number of studies appeared for 2014 to 2020. The overall trend shows an increasing focus on the transfer pricing articles over the years.

Figure-3 : Year Wise Publication Trend

3.2. Publication Subjects

In this section, an analysis of significant fields contributing to transfer pricing has been conducted. Only five subjects have been taken relevant to the centrality of transfer pricing as a business strategy. Economic subject has a significant contribution and constitutes the central part of transfer pricing research (see fig. 4.) because transfer pricing as a concept involves the pricing of goods and services, which is the subject of economy. After economics, Business Finance has a significant amount of literature contained on transfer pricing (55 publications) because of the fact transfer pricing involves trade between two related parties where it is carried through various transactions like the transfer of goods and services and providing finance at concessional rates etc. after that management subject consists of the 35 publications on transfer pricing because transfer pricing has some organizational objectives apart from taxation and finance objectives like coordination, cooperation and motivational objectives between the units of an entity. The other subjects that constitute a significant amount of transfer pricing literature are operations research and business, with 20 and 10 publications, respectively.

3.3. Influential Authors

The distribution of articles according to authors is attempted to identify the leading authors contributing to the literature of TP. Analysis show that only four authors (Matsui K, Pfeiffer T, Reichelstein S and Schjelderup G) have authored 3 articles for each and all the rest authors have authored the similar number of publications see (fig, 5).

Figure-4 : Publication Subjects

Figure-5 : Leading Authors

3.4. Publication Outlet

The segregation of articles based on the journals shows that 'European Journal of Operational Research' is host to the maximum number of articles counted as 10, followed by 'Journal of Taxation', which contains nine articles of TP. This is followed by 'Accounting Review, Contemporary Accounting Research, and

National Tax Journal', which contains eight, seven and seven articles respectively see, (fig 6). Most of these journals are Australian Business Deans Council (ABDC) Category and the Association of Business Schools (ABS) category, which signifies that transfer pricing research being an international issue, finds its place quickly in premium journals. Also, publisher analysis has been carried out, which reveals that 30.46% of the sample articles were published by Elsevier see (Table-1). Followed by Wiley for 10.15% publication then 7.81% was published by Springer Nature providing the enough evidence that approx. 75% of sample articles on TP were published by leading publishers.

Figure-6 : Publication of Articles based on Journals

Table-1 : Publisher Analyses

Publisher	Count	Percentage
Elsevier	39	30.46
Wiley	13	10.15
Springer Nature	10	7.81
American Accounting Association	8	6.25
Warren Gorham Lamont Inc	8	6.25
NATL TAX ASSN	6	4.68
Taylor & Francis	6	4.68
Emerald Group Publishing	4	3.12
Routledge	3	2.33

3.5. Country Publication

Distribution of articles according to country wise identifies the countries having contributed significantly to TP research. Country-wise analysis shows that the USA (66 articles) is the largest contributor to TP research contributing about 51%, followed by Canada (11) contributing about 8.59%, to TP research, see (fig.7). Other countries that are significant contributors are Germany 6.25%, Japan 6.25%, Norway 5.469%, Austria 4.688%, Denmark 3.906%, and South Korea 3.906%.

Figure-7 : Country Wise Analysis

3.6. Co-Authorship Analysis

Co-authorship analysis has been conducted to identify the authors that have linked up for the productivity of TP research. Our sample shows that at least two authors co-authored 23 articles see (Table-2). Co-authorship analysis explains the type and scope of partnerships between co-authors (Kumar et al., 2021) and the regional contribution to knowledge generation on TP research. Our review establishes that Matsui and Kenji have collaborated for the maximum number of documents, three, then Croker, Je and Bimkranth have collaborated for two papers. Mescal and Devan also collaborated on two articles. Likewise, Klassen and Kenneth co-authored two documents, while others who collaborated on two documents are Johnson and Nicole Bastian, Rossing and Christian Plesner, Park and Kunsoo etc. Reichelstein received a maximum number of citations(121) followed by the Park, Kun Soo (59), then Vaysman, I (58), Klassen, Kenneth j (52),

Mescall, devan(52), Rossing, Christian Pesner(42) are the authors who have received a significant amount of citations for their articles may be due to fact of collaboration as interchanging of ideas contributes to knowledge generation.

Co-authorship based on regions shows the countries having a significant amount of documents TP and their connectivity with other countries see (fig 8). The criteria set for this analysis is that countries have the minimum number of papers and citations of 3 and 30, respectively. Our analysis shows that the USA hosts the maximum number of documents (50), with 1374 citations collaborating with Austria and Netherlands. Then Canada has ten papers with 277 citations having main connectivity with China, Portugal and South Korea. Also, Japan has eight documents with 55 citations and connectivity with Germany and Norway while collaborating for TP research. England also is the producer of 8 documents with 80 citations having connectivity with Denmark and Scotland. Germany has seven documents with 65 citations, Norway has seven documents with 90 citations, South Korea has five documents with 74 citations, Austria has six documents with 100 citations, Denmark has five documents with 105 citations, and the Netherlands has three documents with 186 citations etc.

Table-2 : Co-Authorship Analysis

Authors	Documents	Citations	Link Strength
Birnkrant, hj	2	2	2
Buckley, pj	2	8	2
Bucks, dr	2		0
Croker, je	2	2	2
Emmanuel, clive	2	2	0
Gresik, thomas a	2	2	0
Hughes, jf	2	8	2
Johnson, nicole bastin	2	30	1
Klassen, kenneth j.	2	52	2
Matsui, kenji	3	26	0
Mescall, devan	2	52	2
Okoshi, hirofumi"	2	3	0

(Contd...)

Park, kun soo	2	59	0
Pfeiffer, Thomas	2	33	1
Pinho, carlos	2	26	0
Reichelstein, s	2	121	0
Ronen, j	2	14	0
Rossing, christian plen	2	42	0
Schjelderup, g	2	22	1
Srinidhi, b	2	43	0
Vaysman, i"	2	58	0
Weichenrieder, aj	2	25	1

Figure-8 : Co-authorship Linkage Based on Countries

3.7. Keyword Co-occurrence Analysis

A keyword co-occurrence analysis was performed in VOS viewer utilizing all terms from 128 articles to identify the subjects that might reflect concerns in TP

research over time. The concept underpinning this study implies that keywords reflect the article's content (Kumar et al., 2021). Our keyword analysis shows several trends in TP literature over time see (fig 9). Research on TP from 2008 to 2010 was centralized around decentralization, allocation of investment and cost, multinational firms, incentives, taxes etc. because transfer pricing was used more as a strategy to bring efficiency through divisionalization and incentives generated from different countries through tax rates were embarked upon to save on taxes by allocating cost and revenues among subsidiaries. Then from 2010 to 2014, the focus was on international transfer pricing, rules, arm's length principle, model development, impact on economies etc., because countries began to frame and adopt more strict transfer pricing regulations in their tax laws to plug the tax loss of their respective jurisdictions.

Figure-9 : Keyword Co-occurrence Linkage

3.8. Citation Analysis

Citation analysis has been conducted to identify the most cited article, and this analysis shows that Clausing, ka (2003) has the highest number of citations for the article titled Tax Motivated Transfer Pricing And US Intra-Firm Trade Prices, followed by Bertelsman,EJ; Beetsma,rmwj with 164 citations see (Table-3).

Table-3 : Citation Analysis Based on Title and Authors

Rank	Title of study	Author	Citations	Year
1	Tax Motivated Transfer Pricing And US Intra Firm Trade Prices	Clausing, ka	194	2003
2	Why Pay More? Corporate Tax Avoidance Through Transfer Pricing In OECD Countries.	Bartelsman,ej; Beetsma, rmwj	164	2003
3	Taxes And Transfer Pricing: Income Shifting And The Volume Of Intra Firm Transfers.	Jacob,j	85	1996
4	Tax Reforms And Evidence Of Transfer Pricing	Swenson. dl	83	2001
5	Strategic Transfer Pricing	Alles,m; Dater,s	79	1998
6	Integrating Manegrial And Tax Objectives In Transfer Pricing	Baldenius,t;Melumad ,nd; Riechelstein,s	70	2004
7	Specific Investment Under Negotiated Transfer Pricing- An Efficiency Result	Edlin,as; Reichelstein,s	51	1995
8	Strategic Transfer Pricing In A Marketing Operations Interface With Quality Level And Advertising Dependent By Goodwill	Liu,guowei; Zhang,jianxiong; Tang,wansheng	46	2015
9	Transfer Pricing By Multinational Firms; New Evidence From Foreign Ownership	Cristea,ancad; Nguyen,Daniel x	44	2016
10	Transfer Pricing: Strategies,Practices And Tax Minimization	Klassen,Kenneth j; Lisowsky,petro; Mescall, devan	42	2017
11	Negotiated Transfer Pricing And Divisional Vs Firm-Wide Performance Evaluation	Anctil; Dutta	38	1999
12	A Model Of Negotiated Transfer Pricing	vaysman	37	1998

Note: top 12 papers selected on the basis of global citations.

Network visualization has been done to show the linkage between these authors see Figure-10.

Figure-10 : Linkage of Most Cited Authors

4. Results and Discussion

The current literature was reviewed to map the bibliometric aspects and knowledge structure of Transfer Pricing. The bibliometric study generally sheds light on the most prominent authors, nations, journals, subjects, and citations, from 1989 to 2021 (32 years). Different types of analysis that we performed, like co-authorship, citation, keyword co-occurrence, and network analysis etc, helped us draw the following inferences.

- ✓ Research on transfer pricing has received significant importance over time with changing concerns.
- ✓ Highest number of publications appeared after 2014, and the maximum number of publications appeared on the subject of economics.
- ✓ The Maximum numbers of articles were written by Matsui K, Pfeiffer T, Reichelstein S and Schjelderup G, and the highest cited (194) article appeared for clausing, entitled 'tax-motivated transfer pricing and US intra firm trade prices'.

- ✓ European journal of operations research is home to the maximum number (10) of transfer pricing research, followed by the journal of taxation (8). At the same time, Elsevier appeared to be the largest publisher (39 articles) of TP research, followed by Wiley (10).
- ✓ USA is the most significant contributor to TP research contributing about 51% of TP research and 1374 citations having central collaboration with Austria and the Netherlands. Followed by Canada (11), contributing about 8.59% with 277 citations having main connectivity with the people's republic of china, Portugal and South Korea.
- ✓ 23 documents were co-authored based on the criteria of authors who co-authored at least two documents, and Matsui, and Kenji have evolved as co-authors of 3 documents with 26 citations.
- ✓ There has been a shift in research content on transfer pricing over time, divisionalization, resource allocation, coordination and internationalization from 2008 to 2010 and tax compliance, rules, models, arms' length principle etc., from 2010 onwards. Most cited author linkages were found for clausing, ka (194 citations) with Jacob and Klassen followed by Bertelsman (164) citations whose primary linkages were found with Cristea and Swenson.

5. Conclusion and Future Direction

The expansion of globalization and industrialization brought about the emergence of multinational corporations (MNCs), which have experienced a remarkable increase in intra-company trade volume and level due to efforts to expand transactions. Additionally, MNCs have employed transfer pricing tactics to maximize profitability and satisfy stakeholders. Discrepancies in tax rates and regulations across different countries are seen as a key motivator for transfer pricing. This practice has a direct impact on an enterprise's cost, revenue, and overall profitability, making it crucial for their success..

Using a systematic review approach, we were able to analyze the intellectual structure of Transfer Pricing (TP) and conduct bibliometric evaluations to identify its current use in research. Our review indicates that TP is predominantly used as a strategy to avoid taxes, causing a depletion of tax revenues in high-tax countries, particularly in developing nations, by transferring funds to lower-tax countries. The problem of transfer pricing poses a significant challenge for both multinational enterprises (MNEs) and tax authorities..

Our literature review revealed that although tax avoidance is the primary driver behind Transfer Pricing, various non-tax factors also play a crucial role in determining intra-firm trade flows. Research conducted by Hardi Kusuma (2017) and Ronan Merle et al. (2019) demonstrates the impact of non-tax variables, including factors such as size, leverage, intangibility, organizational culture, divisional leadership morale, political environment, and corporate governance. Further exploration of these factors is necessary to understand how transfer pricing practices react to changes in these variables. Also, the majority of the countries began to adopt the Arm's Length principle, Advance Pricing Agreements, Safe Harbour Rules etc, to avoid the transfer pricing disputes in their regions and prevent their tax base, but there is a dearth of literature on how these developments in TP legislation has impacted the transfer pricing practices of the MNCs, therefore, a comprehensive review on these spurs the gap for future research in the area.

Our bibliometric review found that much of the work on transfer pricing has been conducted in developed nations like the USA. It is highly recommended to take up the transfer pricing research in developing countries, particularly India, as developing nations usually have different economic and fiscal conditions than developed nations. We believe that the changing business environment, both locally and internationally, will keep the area of TP fascinating for researchers, practitioners, and policymakers. Moreover, there is a need for increased collaboration across regions for transfer pricing research.

References

- Ronen, J. (1992). Transfer pricing reconsidered. *Journal of Public Economics*, 47(1), 125-136.
- Dworin, L. (1990). Transfer pricing issues. *National Tax Journal*, 43(3), 285-291.
- Pfeiffer, T., Schiller, U., & Wagner, J. (2011). Cost-based transfer pricing. *Review of Accounting Studies*, 16(2), 219-246.
- Alles, M., & Datar, S. (1998). Strategic transfer pricing. *Management Science*, 44(4), 451-461.
- Kral, K., & Serota, J. (1993). Proposed transfer pricing penalty amendment. *Journal of Accountancy*, 175(7), 29.
- Chalos, P., & Haka, S. (1990). Transfer pricing under bilateral bargaining. *Accounting Review*, 624-641.
- Nielsen, S. B. (2014). Transfer pricing: roles and regimes. *revista de economia mundial*, 103-122.

- Gabrielsen, T. S., & Schjelderup, G. (1999). Transfer pricing and ownership structure. *Scandinavian Journal of Economics*, 101(4), 673-688.
- Fjell, K., & Foros, Ø. (2008). Access regulation and strategic transfer pricing. *Management Accounting Research*, 19(1), 18-31.
- Buckley, P. J., & Hughes, J. F. (1997). Japanese transfer pricing policy: a note. *Applied Economics Letters*, 4(1), 13-17.
- Vaysman, I. (1998). A model of negotiated transfer pricing. *Journal of Accounting and Economics*, 25(3), 349-384.
- Shor, M., & Chen, H. (2009). Decentralization, transfer pricing and tacit collusion. *Contemporary Accounting Research*, 26(2), 581-604.
- Gresik, T. A., & Osmundsen, P. (2008). Transfer pricing in vertically integrated industries. *International Tax and Public Finance*, 15(3), 231-255.
- Zhao, L. (2000). Decentralization and transfer pricing under oligopoly. *Southern Economic Journal*, 67(2), 414-426.
- RaimondosMøller, P., & Scharf, K. (2002). Transfer pricing rules and competing governments. *Oxford Economic Papers*, 54(2), 230-246.
- Autrey, R. L., & Bova, F. (2012). Gray markets and multinational transfer pricing. *The accounting review*, 87(2), 393-421.
- Avila, M., & Ronen, J. (1999). Transfer-pricing mechanisms: an experimental investigation. *International Journal of Industrial Organization*, 17(5), 689-715.
- Radoloviæ, J. (2012). Transfer pricing model based on multiple-factor transfer pricing model using the transactional net margin method. *Economic research-Ekonomska istra•ivanja*, 25(1), 30-42.
- Choi, J. P., Furusawa, T., & Ishikawa, J. (2020). Transfer pricing regulation and tax competition. *Journal of International Economics*, 127, 103367.
- Schjelderup, G., & Weichenrieder, A. J. (1999). Trade, multinationals, and transfer pricing regulations. *Canadian Journal of Economics*, 817-834.
- Frisch, D. J. (1989). The BALRM approach to transfer pricing. *National Tax Journal*, 42(3), 261-271.
- Jost, S. P., Pfaffermayr, M., & Winner, H. (2014). Transfer pricing as a tax compliance risk. *Accounting and Business Research*, 44(3), 260-279.

- Dikolli, S. S., & Vaysman, I. (2006). Information technology, organizational design, and transfer pricing. *Journal of Accounting and Economics*, 41(1-2), 201-234.
- Solilova, V., & Nerudová, D. (2013). Transfer pricing: general model for tax planning. *Ekonomický časopis (Journal of Economics)*, 6(61), 597-617.
- Elitzur, R., & Mintz, J. (1996). Transfer pricing rules and corporate tax competition. *Journal of Public Economics*, 60(3), 401-422.
- Stewart, J. C. (1989). Transfer pricing: some empirical evidence from Ireland. *Journal of Economic Studies*, 40-56.
- Klassen, K. J., Lisowsky, P., & Mescall, D. (2017). Transfer pricing: Strategies, practices, and tax minimization. *Contemporary Accounting Research*, 34(1), 455-493.
- Fernandes, R., Pinho, C., & Gouveia, B. (2015). Supply chain networks design and transfer-pricing. *The international journal of logistics management*, 26(1), 428-446.
- Al-Eryani, M. F., Alam, P., & Akhter, S. H. (1990). Transfer pricing determinants of US multinationals. *Journal of International Business Studies*, 21(3), 409-425.
- Dutta, S., & Reichelstein, S. (2021). Capacity Rights and Full-Cost Transfer Pricing. *Management Science*, 67(2), 1303-1325.
- Rogers, H., & Oats, L. (2022, January). Transfer pricing: changing views in changing times. In *Accounting Forum* (Vol. 46, No. 1, pp. 83-107). Routledge.
- Swenson, D. L. (2001). Tax reforms and evidence of transfer pricing. *National Tax Journal*, 54(1), 7-25.
- Juranek, S., Schindler, D., & Schjelderup, G. (2018). Transfer pricing regulation and taxation of royalty payments. *Journal of Public Economic Theory*, 20(1), 67-84.
- Stevenson, T. H., & Cabell, D. W. (2002). Integrating transfer pricing policy and activity-based costing. *Journal of International Marketing*, 10(4), 77-88.
- Behrens, K., Peralt, S., & Picard, P. M. (2014). Transfer pricing rules, OECD guidelines, and market distortions. *Journal of Public Economic Theory*, 16(4), 650-680.
- Erickson, G. M. (2012). Transfer pricing in a dynamic marketing-operations interface. *European Journal of Operational Research*, 216(2), 326-333.
- Chen, C. H. (2005). Case study application of VSM to transfer pricing. *Systemic Practice and Action Research*, 18(4), 379-394.
- Adams, L., & Drtina, R. (2008). Transfer pricing for aligning divisional and corporate decisions. *Business Horizons*, 51(5), 411-417.

- Dicker, L. J., & Carlson, G. N. (1992). The Proposed Transfer Pricing Regulations: Comments and Concerns. *National Tax Journal*, 45(3), 233-238.
- Dejong, D. V., Forsythe, R., Kim, J. O., & Uecker, W. C. (1989). A laboratory investigation of alternative transfer pricing mechanisms. *Accounting, Organizations and Society*, 14(1-2), 41-64.
- Baldenius, T., Melumad, N. D., & Reichelstein, S. (2004). Integrating managerial and tax objectives in transfer pricing. *The accounting review*, 79(3), 591-615.
- Johnson, E., Johnson, N. B., & Pfeiffer, T. (2016). Dual transfer pricing with internal and external trade. *Review of Accounting Studies*, 21(1), 140-164.
- De Waegenaere, A., Sansing, R. C., & Wielhouwer, J. L. (2006). Who benefits from inconsistent multinational tax transferpricing rules?. *Contemporary Accounting Research*, 23(1), 103-131.
- Johnson, N. B. (2006). Divisional performance measurement and transfer pricing for intangible assets. *Review of Accounting Studies*, 11(2), 339-365.
- Mackevicius, J., & Novikovas, M. (2012). TRANSFER PRICING MODEL FOR TAX PAYERS AND TAX ADMINISTRATORS. *Transformations in Business & Economics*, 11(3).
- Clausing, K. A. (2003). Tax-motivated transfer pricing and US intrafirm trade prices. *Journal of Public Economics*, 87(9-10), 2207-2223.
- Buckley, P. J., & Hughes, J. F. (1998). Transfer pricing and economic functions analysis: the Japanese paradigm. *Applied Economics*, 30(5), 621-629.
- Blouin, J. L., Robinson, L. A., & Seidman, J. K. (2018). Conflicting transfer pricing incentives and the role of coordination. *Contemporary Accounting Research*, 35(1), 87-116.
- Matsui, K. (2011). Strategic transfer pricing and social welfare under product differentiation. *European Accounting Review*, 20(3), 521-550.
- Kachelmeier, S. J., & Towry, K. L. (2002). Negotiated transfer pricing: Is fairness easier said than done?. *The Accounting Review*, 77(3), 571-593.
- Besanko, D., & Sibley, D. S. (1991). Compensation and transfer pricing in a principal-agent model. *International Economic Review*, 55-68.
- Kim, Y. G. (2007). How Do Korean Multi-National Firms Decide International Transfer Pricing. *Journal of Korea Trade*, 11(1), 173-200.
- Prusa, T. J. (1990). An incentive compatible approach to the transfer pricing problem. *Journal of International Economics*, 28(1-2), 155-172.

- Edlin, A. S., & Reichelstein, S. (1995). Specific investment under negotiated transfer pricing: An efficiency result. *Accounting Review*, 275-291.
- Saltzman, M. I. (1993). TRANSFER PRICING PENALTY PROPOSED REGS LIMIT REASONABLE CAUSE EXCEPTION. *Journal of Taxation*, 79(4), 252-257.
- Zhao, L. (1998). Labour-management bargaining and transfer pricing in multinational corporations. *Canadian Journal of Economics*, 817-829.
- Weichenrieder, A. J. (1996). Transfer pricing, double taxation, and the cost of capital. *The Scandinavian Journal of Economics*, 445-452.
- Tisdell, C. A. (1989). Transfer pricing: technical and productivity change within the firm. *Managerial and Decision Economics*, 10(3), 253-256.
- De Mooij, R., & Liu, L. (2020). At a cost: The real effects of transfer pricing regulations. *IMF Economic Review*, 68(1), 268-306.
- Levey, M. M., Ruchelman, S. C., & Seto, W. R. (1989). Transfer Pricing of Intangibles after the Section-482 White Paper. *Journal of Taxation*, 71(1), 38.
- Lantz, B. (2009). The double marginalization problem of transfer pricing: Theory and experiment. *European Journal of Operational Research*, 196(2), 434-439.
- Cools, M., Emmanuel, C., & Jorissen, A. (2008). Management control in the transfer pricing tax compliant multinational enterprise. *Accounting, Organizations and Society*, 33(6), 603-628.
- Perèeviaè, H., & Hladika, M. (2017). Application of transfer pricing methods in related companies in Croatia. *Economic research-Ekonomska istra•ivanja*, 30(1), 611-628.
- Miller, T., & De Matta, R. (2008). A global supply chain profit maximization and transfer pricing model. *Journal of Business Logistics*, 29(1), 175-199.
- Leng, M., & Parlar, M. (2012). Transfer pricing in a multidivisional firm: A cooperative game analysis. *Operations Research Letters*, 40(5), 364-369.
- Wang, Z., Gao, W., & Mukhopadhyay, S. K. (2016). Impact of taxation on international transfer pricing and offshoring decisions. *Annals of Operations Research*, 240(2), 683-707.
- Barry, F. (2005). FDI, transfer pricing and the measurement of R&D intensity. *Research Policy*, 34(5), 673-681.
- Granwell, A. W., & Klein, K. (1992). Objective Tests of Transfer Pricing Prop Regs Require Subjective Determinations. *Journal of Taxation*, 76(5), 308-315.

- Ancil, R. M., & Dutta, S. (1999). Negotiated transfer pricing and divisional vs. firmwide performance evaluation. *The Accounting Review*, 74(1), 87-104.
- Engle, H. S. (1993). TRANSFER PRICING-THE NEW SECTION 482 TEMPORARY AND PROPOSED REGULATIONS. *Journal of Corporate Taxation*, 20(3), 223-236.
- Elliot, V. (2018). Funds Transfer Pricing in Swedish Savings Banks: An Exploratory Survey. *Scandinavian Journal of Management*, 34(3), 289-302.
- Bernard, J. T., & Genest-Laplante, E. (1996). Transfer pricing by the Canadian oil industry: a company analysis. *Applied Economics Letters*, 3(5), 333-340.
- Becker, J., & Fuest, C. (2012). Transfer pricing policy and the intensity of tax rate competition. *Economics Letters*, 117(1), 146-148.
- Stoughton, N. M., & Talmor, E. (1994). A mechanism design approach to transfer pricing by the multinational firm. *European Economic Review*, 38(1), 143-170.
- Bucks, D. R., & Mazerov, M. (1993). The state solution to the federal government's international transfer pricing problem. *National Tax Journal*, 46(3), 385-392.
- Mukunoki, H., & Okoshi, H. (2021). Tariff elimination versus tax avoidance: Free trade agreements and transfer pricing. *International Tax and Public Finance*, 28(5), 1188-1210.
- Mura, A., Emmanuel, C., & Vallascas, F. (2013). Challenging the reliability of comparables under profit-based transfer pricing methods. *Accounting and Business Research*, 43(5), 483-505.
- Matsui, K. (2013). Entry deterrence through credible commitment to transfer pricing at direct cost. *Management accounting research*, 24(3), 261-275.
- Abdallah, W. M. (1989). How to motivate and evaluate managers with international transfer pricing systems. *Management International Review*, 29(1), 65.
- Villegas, F., & Ouenniche, J. (2008). A general unconstrained model for transfer pricing in multinational supply chains. *European Journal of Operational Research*, 187(3), 829-856.
- De Waegenare, A., Sansing, R., & Wielhouwer, J. L. (2007). Using bilateral advance pricing agreements to resolve tax transfer pricing disputes. *National Tax Journal*, 60(2), 173-191.
- Choe, C., & Hyde, C. E. (2007). Multinational transfer pricing, tax arbitrage and the arm's length principle. *Economic Record*, 83(263), 398-404.
- Smith, C. M. (1994). Documentation Needed to Avoid Penalties Specified by Transfer Pricing Temp Regs. *Journal of Taxation*, 80(5), 304-308.

- Kumar, S., Pandey, N., Lim, W. M., Chatterjee, A. N., & Pandey, N. (2021). What do we know about transfer pricing? Insights from bibliometric analysis. *Journal of Business research*, 134, 275-287.
- Cristea, A. D., & Nguyen, D. X. (2016). Transfer pricing by multinational firms: New evidence from foreign firm ownerships. *American Economic Journal: Economic Policy*, 8(3), 170-202.
- Bradford, D. F. (2003). Addressing the Transfer-pricing Problem in an Origin-basis X Tax. *International Tax and Public Finance*, 10(5), 591-610.
- Rossing, C. P. (2013). Tax strategy control: The case of transfer pricing tax risk management. *Management Accounting Research*, 24(2), 175-194.
- Matsui, K. (2011). Intrafirm trade, arm's-length transfer pricing rule, and coordination failure. *European Journal of Operational Research*, 212(3), 570-582.
- Ceran, Y., Dawande, M., Liu, D., & Mookerjee, V. (2014). Optimal software reuse in incremental software development: A transfer pricing approach. *Management Science*, 60(3), 541-559.
- Timo, S., Martin, K., & Ali, Y. K. (2014). Global Supply Chain and transfer pricing'. *Supply Chain Management-An International Journal*, 19(4), 445-454.
- Kari, S., & Ylä-Liedenpohja, J. (2005). Effects of an Equalization Tax on Multinational Investments and Transfer Pricing. *FinanzArchiv/Public Finance Analysis*, 45-61.
- Löffler, C. (2019). Divisionalization and domestic transfer pricing for tax considerations in the multinational enterprise. *Management Accounting Research*, 45, 100646.
- Chan, K. H., & Chow, L. (1997). An empirical study of tax audits in China on international transfer pricing. *Journal of Accounting and Economics*, 23(1), 83-112.
- Colbert, G. J., & Spicer, B. H. (1995). A multi-case investigation of a theory of the transfer pricing process. *Accounting, Organizations and Society*, 20(6), 423-456.
- Lakhal, S. Y. (2006). An operational profit sharing and transfer pricing model for network-manufacturing companies. *European Journal of Operational Research*, 175(1), 543-565.
- Rossing, C. P., & Rohde, C. (2010). Overhead cost allocation changes in a transfer pricing tax compliant multinational enterprise. *Management Accounting Research*, 21(3), 199-216.
- Li, S. H., & Balachandran, K. R. (1997). Optimal transfer pricing schemes for work averse division managers with private information. *European Journal of Operational Research*, 98(1), 138-153.

- Copithorne, L. W. (1971). International corporate transfer prices and government policy. *The Canadian Journal of Economics/Revue canadienne d'Economique*, 4(3), 324-341.
- Devi, D.K., & Suryarini, T. (2020). The Effect of Tax Minimization and Exchange Rate on Transfer Pricing Decisions with Leverage as Moderating. *Accounting Analysis Journal*, 9(2), 110-115.
- Richardson, G., Taylor, G., & Lanis, R. (2013). Determinants of transfer pricing aggressiveness: Empirical evidence from Australian firms. *Journal of Contemporary Accounting and Economics*, 9(2), 136-150. doi:10.1016/j.jcae.2013.06.002
- Donnenfeld, S., Prusa, T. J., Journal, S., & June, N. (1995). *Monitoring and Coordination in MNCs: Implications for Transfer Pricing and Intra-Firm Trade*. 10(2), 230-255.
- Egger, P., & Seidel, T. (2013). Corporate taxes and intra-firm trade. *European Economic Review*, 63, 225-242. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eurocorev.2013.07.007>
- Grubert, H., & Mutti, J. (1991). Taxes, Tariffs and Transfer Pricing in Multinational Corporate Decision Making. In *Source: The Review of Economics and Statistics* (Vol. 73, Issue 2).
- Overesch, M. (2006). Transfer pricing of intrafirm sales as a profit shifting channel- Evidence from German firm data. *ZEW-Centre for European Economic Research Discussion Paper*, (06-084).
- Pendse, S. J. (2012). *International transfer pricing: A review of non-tax outlook*. 37, 337-343. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2012.03.299>
- Vicard, V. (2014). *Profit shifting through transfer pricing: evidence from French firm level trade data* *. <http://www.impots>.
- Sebele-Mpofu, Eukeria Mashiri & Samantha Chantelle Schwartz | Collins G. Ntim (Reviewing editor) (2021) An exposition of transfer pricing motives, strategies and their implementation in tax avoidance by MNEs in developing countries, *Cogent Business & Management*, 8:1, DOI: 10.1080/23311975.2021.1944007
- Grabski, S. V. (1985). Transfer pricing in complex organizations: A review and integration of recent empirical and analytical research. *Readings in accounting for management control*, 453-495.
- Padhi, S. K. (2019). Transfer pricing a review of literature. *Transferencia de precios, revisión de la literatura*. *International Journal of Advanced Research in Management*, 10(1), 1-7.

- Septiani, D. H., Prawira, I. F. A., & Kustiawan, M. (2021). Transfer Pricing, A Tax Avoidance Tool (A Review of Literature). *Nusantara Science and Technology Proceedings*, 404-411.
- birnkrant, h., & croker, j. (1994). despite improvements, transfer pricing regs still carry a risk of double taxation. *journal of taxation*, 81(6), 332-337.
- Glicklich, P. A., & Goldstein, S. B. (1993). new transfer pricing regs adhere more closely to an arms-length standard. *Journal of Taxation*, 78(5), 306-314.
- Pfeiffer, T. (1999). Transfer pricing and decentralized dynamic lot-sizing in multistage, multiproduct production processes. *European Journal of Operational Research*, 116(2), 319-330.
- Sari, D., & Utama, S. Fitriany, and Rahayu, N.(2020). Transfer Pricing Practices and Specific Anti-Avoidance Rules in Asian Developing Countries. *International Journal of Emerging Markets*, Vol. ahead-of-print No. ahead-of-print. [https://doi, 10](https://doi.org/10.1108/IJEM-01-2020-0010).
- birnkrant, h., & croker, j. (1994). transfer pricing final regs increase flexibility, but not certainty, in choice of method. *journal of taxation*, 81(5), 268-273.
- Mescall, D., & Klassen, K. J. (2018). How Does Transfer Pricing Risk Affect Premiums in CrossBorder Mergers and Acquisitions?. *Contemporary Accounting Research*, 35(2), 830-865.
- Bhattacharjee, S., & Moreno, K. K. (2017). The role of informal controls and a bargaining opponent's emotions on transfer pricing judgments. *Contemporary Accounting Research*, 34(1), 427-454.
- Liu, G., Zhang, J., & Tang, W. (2015). Strategic transfer pricing in a marketing–operations interface with quality level and advertising dependent goodwill. *Omega*, 56, 1-15.
- Mescall, D., & Klassen, K. J. (2018). How Does Transfer Pricing Risk Affect Premiums in CrossBorder Mergers and Acquisitions?. *Contemporary Accounting Research*, 35(2), 830-865.
- Martini, J. T., Niemann, R., & Simons, D. (2012). Transfer pricing or formula apportionment? Taxinduced distortions of multinationals' investment and production decisions. *Contemporary Accounting Research*, 29(4), 1060-1086.
- Johanson, J., & Vahlne, J. E. (2017). The internationalization process of the firm—a model of knowledge development and increasing foreign market commitments. In *International business* (pp. 145-154).